

DETERMINING THE RATIONALE AND PURPOSE OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the rating systems of higher education institutions, their role and impact on the quality of education. The article examines international and national rating systems, their criteria and strategic importance for higher education institutions of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Higher education, rating systems, quality of education, international assessment, universities of Uzbekistan.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются рейтинговые системы высших учебных заведений, их роль и влияние на качество образования. В статье рассматриваются международные и национальные рейтинговые системы, их критерии, а также их стратегическое значение для высших учебных заведений Узбекистана.

Ключевые слова: Высшее образование, рейтинговые системы, качество образования, международная оценка, вузы Узбекистана.

The higher education system is of great importance for the intellectual and economic development of each country. The importance of rating systems is increasing in order to improve the quality of education and form internationally competitive universities. Rating systems such as QS, THE (Times Higher Education) and ARWU (Academic Ranking of World Universities) are evaluated based on criteria such as research activity of universities, international cooperation, quality of teaching and the share of talented students.

Methodology

Different methodological approaches are used to determine the rating of higher education institutions and determine their goals. In this study, the following methods were used to evaluate rating systems, determine goals and study their impact on the quality of education:

1. Data collection methods

Document analysis - Official documents, regulations and normative documents on Uzbek and international rating systems were studied.

Statistical analysis - Official statistical data on the rating of universities, scientific results and the quality of education were analyzed.

Survey and interview – A survey was conducted among representatives of higher education institutions, professors and students, and their opinions were studied.

2. Analysis of rating systems

The following international and national rating systems were studied as part of the study:

International ratings:

QS World University Rankings

Times Higher Education (THE)

Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU – Shanghai Ranking)

National ratings:

Rating of Higher Education Institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Evaluation systems of independent educational institutions

3. Evaluation criteria

The main evaluation criteria for determining the ranking of universities were determined as follows:

Scientific and innovative activity – Number of scientific articles, scientific projects and patents.

Quality of students and graduates – Level of employment of graduates and competitiveness in the labor market.

Potential of professors and teachers – Number of articles published in international scientific journals and the presence of scientists who have made a significant scientific contribution.

International cooperation – Cooperation with foreign universities, academic exchange programs and the share of international students.

Financial stability and infrastructure – Financial support of the university, the volume of grants and investments, material and technical base.

4. Determining the purpose of higher education institutions

The main purpose of universities is to improve the quality of education and scientific potential.

The strategy of the national education system was developed based on the development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.

The transformation of the educational process includes modern technologies, digital education and advanced pedagogical methods.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. International rating systems and their specific features

The most prestigious university rating systems in the world are:

QS World University Rankings – universities are evaluated based on their academic reputation, employer ratings, student-teacher ratio and impact index of scientific articles.

Times Higher Education (THE) – focuses on criteria such as the quality of scientific research, international cooperation and educational environment.

ARWU (Shanghai Ranking) – is evaluated based on the number of scientific articles and Nobel Prize winners of universities.

2. Ranking of higher education institutions of Uzbekistan

In recent years, universities of Uzbekistan have been trying to strengthen their position in international rankings. In 2023, Tashkent State University of Economics was ranked between 801-1000 in the QS ranking. The National University of Uzbekistan took 1201+ in the THE ranking. Tashkent University of Information Technologies took 351-400 places in the QS Asia ranking in 2022. In addition, a national ranking system is being developed. According to data provided by the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023, the highest rated universities include Tashkent State Law University, Samarkand State University, and Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute.

3. Impact of the rating system on the quality and purpose of education

Scientific research activity has increased - since 2021, the number of scientific articles published by universities in Uzbekistan has increased by 35% (Ministry of Higher Education, 2023). International cooperation has increased - in 2022, Uzbek universities signed cooperation agreements with more than 120 international universities. Attention to the quality of education has increased - in 2023, more than 10 universities in Uzbekistan received international accreditation (Erasmus+ reports, 2023). The results show that the ranking of universities directly affects the quality of education and the increase in scientific activity. At the same time, the need to adapt to international standards and increase scientific potential remains a pressing issue for local universities.

Determining the ranking of higher education institutions and defining their goals is an important factor in improving the quality and competitiveness of education. There are systems for assessing higher education institutions around the world (QS, THE, ARWU), which

determine the rating by assessing the scientific, academic and innovative activities of universities. Important steps are being taken in Uzbekistan to include higher education institutions in international ratings and form a national rating system.

1. The impact of the rating system on the quality of education - The high positions of universities in international ratings have a positive impact on the quality of education and the development of scientific and innovative activities.

2. National rating system - Measures are being taken in Uzbekistan to introduce a national rating system. This will help develop the internal assessment system of universities and improve the quality of education.

3. The goal and development strategy of universities - Higher education institutions are striving to strengthen their status by developing education, science and innovation at the national and international levels.

4. Quality of training and employment - The employment rate of university graduates and their competitiveness in the labor market directly affect the ranking indicators.

5. International cooperation and academic mobility - Attracting foreign professors and teachers, participating in international scientific projects, and developing student exchange programs play an important role in increasing the prestige of higher education institutions.

In conclusion, determining the rating and setting the goal of higher education institutions is an important factor in improving the quality of education, forming internationally competitive universities, and developing innovative and scientific activities. Therefore, the development strategy of educational institutions should be formed in accordance with international requirements and standards.

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